

Action of Metal Ions and some Common Organic Compounds on *E. histolytica* and Possible Synergistic Effects of Surfactants and Bile Salts and Drugs on *E. histolytica*

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Studies on the action of metal ions and some simple organic compounds on *E. histolytica* prepared axenically in a modified Diamond TPS-1 medium have been made. The compounds paranitrobenzoic acid, 2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline show considerable antiamebic activities. The variations of lethal activities of different metal ions have also been analysed. Studies on the possible synergistic effects of bile salts or surfactants together with some common drugs have also been made.

In course of our studies on the synthesis of new antiamebic drugs based on the physicochemical properties of different known antiamebic drugs, we considered that some common organic chemicals with biological activities, like benzoic acid, *p*-nitrobenzoic acid (PNBA), *p*-aminobenzoic acid, salicylic acid, *p*-aminosalicylic acid (PASA), 2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline may be tested for antiamebic activities.

The inhibitory action of bile salts on *E. histolytica* has been demonstrated by a number of workers¹⁻⁴. Inadequate bile salt production has been suggested to be one of the important factors that directly or indirectly influences the host-parasite or ameba-bacteria relationships in human intestine. The bile salts or surfactants lower the surface tension of the media which probably result in suppressing the multiplication of ameba¹. It is, therefore, desirable to study the synergistic or additive effects of some bile salts (sodium taurocholate, sodium tauroglycolate) or surfactants (sodium lauryl sulphate, Tween-80) at non-lethal concentrations together with known drugs like metronidazole, tinidazole and spiroamine hydrochloride (found to be antiamebic in nature in our previous investigation) on *E. histolytica*. The action of various metallic inhibitors on *E. histolytica* also deserves attention⁴⁻⁷. The inhibitory effects of different metal ions may give some important informations regarding the drug metabolism and mechanism of drug action. We, therefore, carried out the action of metallic inhibitors on the axenically grown *E. histolytica*.

Experimental

All the chemical used in the study of the inhibitory activities were of guaranteed quality.

E. histolytica (L.D. Strain) was grown axenically in the modified TPS-1 Diamond medium⁸ described

in our previous communication⁹. We have, however, eliminated horse serum (or bovine serum as used by Dutta and Rao¹⁰) as well as ascorbic acid. The bacterial flora was eradicated by treatment with gention violet and acriflavine¹¹. The use of antibiotics was also avoided. Sufficient NaOH (~1 *N*) was added to the broth to adjust the pH to 7 or little above. The broth was autoclaved and stored at 4°.

The cultures of ameba and antiamebic screening of the compounds were done as reported earlier^{9,12,13}. Seven days old culture was used as inoculum and the tubes containing ~20 × 10⁴ ameba ml⁻¹ were used for studying the inhibitory concentrations of the compounds termed as drugs. The drug suspension in normal saline (1 ml) was added in each culture tube (containing 8.8 ml of medium and 0.2 ml inoculum) in duplicate to give a concentration of 1000 μg ml⁻¹ for the trial compounds. Eight successive two-fold serial dilutions of the compounds in normal saline were made and the compounds were added in a way described before in subsequent duplicate tubes. Strict aseptic condition was maintained. Drug dilutions were sterilised by autoclaving (10 lbs/sq inch) for 15 min before test. The tests were run for 48 h and incubation was carried out at 37°. The cultures were examined after 48 h for viable and motile amebae and the amebicidal end points (M.I.C. values) were noted. The results were further confirmed by subculture. The reproducibility of the results were confirmed by repeating the operations 16 times.

To study the synergistic effects of bile salts or surfactant, a constant amount (31.5–63.0 μg ml⁻¹) of non-lethal concentrations of the substances like Tween-80, sodium lauryl sulphate, sodium taurocholate and sodium tauroglycolate together with the desired drug was taken. The non-inhibitory concentrations of bile salts or surfactants were maintained in the successive serial dilutions of the drugs.

The testing was done in the usual way. The results are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—*In vitro* ACTIVITIES* OF AMOEBCIDAL DRUGS

Compd.	MIC ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) 48 h
PABA	Nil
PASA	Nil
PNBA	15.625
Benzoic acid	Nil
Salicylic acid	Nil
2,2'-Dipyridyl	31.25
1,10-Phenanthroline	15.625
CuSO ₄	62.5
MgSO ₄	62.5
ZnSO ₄	31.25
FeSO ₄	31.25
MnSO ₄	7.81
CaSO ₄	7.81
CdSO ₄	7.81
NiSO ₄	7.81

*MIC=Minimum inhibitory concentration; Amebae concentration in each tube=22000-23000 per ml.

TABLE 2—AMEBICIDAL ACTION OF METRONIDAZOLE (A), TINIDAZOLE (B) and SPIROAMINE HYDROCHLORIDE (C) WITH SURFACE ACTIVE AGENTS AND BILE SALTS*

Sl. no.	Compd.*	MIC of drugs
1.	A	3.89
	A+e	3.89
	A+f	3.89
	A+g	3.89
	A+h	3.89
	Control	No effect
2.	B	1.94
	B+e	1.94
	B+f	1.94
	B+g	1.94
	B+h	1.94
	Control	No effect
3.	C	15.8-7.78
	C+e	15.8-7.78
	C+f	15.8-7.78
	C+g	15.8-7.78
	C+h	15.8-7.78
	Control	No effect

*Concn. of surface active agents (e, f, g or h)=31.125-62.250 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$; pH=7.0-7.4; Amebae concentration in each tube=23000-24000 per ml. **e=Sodium taurocholate, f=sodium tauroglycolate, g=sodium lauryl sulphate, h=Tween-80.

Results and Discussion

Fairly water-soluble compounds like PABA, PASA, benzoic acid and salicylic acid have been found to be inactive though some of them have chelating properties. But the slightly soluble compounds like PNBA (with no chelating property), 2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline (well known chelating agents) have been found to be effective as amebicides. The results suggest that low water-solubility and high lipid-solubility are essential for the compounds to be amebicides. The high lipid-solubility is essential for the penetration of the cell wall on *E. histolytica*.

The amebastatic effects of surface active agents and bile salts on the growth of *E. histolytica* are probably due to the lowering of surface tension of the medium resulting in suppression of multiplication of ameba. It has been suggested that in case of intestinal amebiasis, the trophozoites of *E. histolytica* would be exposed to naturally occurring surfactants (like salts of bile acids and fatty acids) effecting the lowering of surface tension of the intestinal contents and leading to the prevention of colonisation by ameba. Thus, a low lipid diet or an inadequate excretion of bile salts increases surface tension of the intestinal contents and favours colonisation of the lower intestinal tract⁴.

The inhibitory concentrations of some of the bile salts in axenic cultures of *E. histolytica* have been reported²⁻⁴ as follows: sodium cholate, 4000; sodium taurocholate, 2000; sodium deoxycholate 500 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The total bile salt secretion is highly variable. Fasting or a carbohydrate diet lowers but high protein diet increases the secretion of bile salts.

However, the concentrations should be regarded to be too high to regard these compounds as true amebicides. We feel that compound having inhibitory concentration of 125 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ or more should not be regarded as an effective amebicide. We, therefore, maintained the non-lethal concentrations 31.5-63.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the bile salts or surfactants in our experiments.

The results (Tables 1 and 2) show that the bile salts and the surfactants used have no influence on the amebicidal end points of the known or possible drug similar to the observations of Dutta and Yadava^{2,3}. The results indicate that tinidazole is more effective than metronidazole. The results also confirm our earlier reports that spiro amino hydrochloride^{1,2} is less effective than metronidazole but can be treated as an effective drug against *E. histolytica* though we could not determine the toxicity and *in vivo* activity of the compound.

The amebicidal activities of *E. histolytica* appear to be little affected by the nature of anion as under the experimental conditions, the metal ions are converted into hydroxides. It has been found that the cations like Mn^{II}, Ca^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ni^{II} are highly lethal to *E. histolytica*, Cu^{II} and Mg^{II} are relatively non-lethal whereas Zn^{II} and Fe^{II} are moderately lethal. The true explanations as to the lethal concentrations of metal ions are very difficult to suggest as the tests were carried out in presence of large amount of extraneous substances where effective concentrations of metal ions are likely to be reduced to different but unknown extents due to hydrolysis, complexations and various possible interactions of metal ions with different constituents of the culture medium.

A number of enzymes like ribonuclease (R-Nase), deoxyribonuclease (D-Nase), α -amylase (responsible for the digestion of starch of *E. histolytica*), fructose-1,6-diphosphate (FDP) aldolase had been isolated from *E. histolytica*. The

metal ions were found to inhibit the different enzymic activities to different extents^{4,14-18}, e.g. at different concentrations.

So the combined effects of the different enzymic activities may be responsible for the difference in the antiamebic activities of the metal ions.

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